

IMPORTANCE OF STERILIZATION METHODS FOR EFFECTIVE CULTIVATION OF DRACOCEPHALUM MOLDOVICA IN VITRO

Otajonova N.S. ¹

Zakirova R.P. ¹

Bashilov A.V. ²

¹ Institute of Chemistry of Plant Substances named after. acad. S.Yu. Yunusov
Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan
Mirzo Ulugbek district, Tashkent, Republic of Uzbekistan
e-mail: nasibakhhozimjonova@gmail.com

² Central Botanical Garden, National Academy of Sciences of Belarus
st. Surganova 2v, Minsk, Minsk region 220012, Belarus
e-mail: anton.v.bashilov@gmail.com
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11353378>

Abstract

Due to the rapid reduction of natural ranges of many wild species of medicinal plants, active human economic activity and global climate change, the conservation of plant biodiversity is of great importance.

Among such medicinal plants are representatives of the *Labiaceae* family, which contain many biologically active substances. *Dracocephalum* species of this family are especially rich in flavonoids. The genus *Dracocephalum* belongs to the family of the clemataceae and includes about 186 species all over the world. *Dracocephalum moldovica* contains many biologically active substances such as monoterpenoids, triterpenoids, phenols, glycosides, polysaccharides, flavonoids and essential oils. Therefore, *in vitro* propagation using cell and tissue cultures to reproduce plants of this family over a large area and to improve the preservation of ecu-materials gives effective results.

Purpose of the study: to select and improve the optimal variants of methods for introducing *Dracocephalum moldovica* plant material into *in vitro* conditions. To reproduce *Dracocephalum moldovica* species *in vitro*, plant seeds were selected and sterilized under special aseptic conditions. The sterilization process was carried out stepwise based on 1% solution of bidentate acid and sterilized water at different intervals.

In sterilization method 1- In sterilization method, seeds were sterilized in 1% Diacid solution for 10 minutes and then washed thoroughly 3 times with sterile water. 2- In the sterilization method, the seeds were sterilized for 10 minutes in 1% Diacid solution, then washed thoroughly 3 times with sterile water, and before planting, the polysaccharide shell of the seeds was lightly set on fire. and planted. In the 3-fold sterilization method, the seeds were sterilized for 5-7

minutes in a 1-fold solution of divalent acid and then left in sterile water 3 times for 3-4 minutes. After sterilization, growth stimulants were used for cultivation. Murashige and Skuta (MS) basic medium was added to the seeds. Seeds sown on nutrient medium were transferred to light room conditions with 16-hour photoperiod, 3000 lux illumination, 60% humidity and 24-26°C and monitored.

When seeds planted on nutrient medium were observed for 15 days, seeds planted by the 1st method germinated from day 9, 3 out of 15 seeds germinated on day 9, 5 seeds on day 12, and 15 seeds on day 15. Out of the seed, 7 seeds germinated. Of the seeds planted by the second method, no plants germinated at all within 15 days. Seeds planted by the third method started germinating on the 6th day, 5 out of 20 seeds germinated on the 6th day, 7 out of 20 seeds on the 9th day, 9 out of 20 seeds on the 12th day, 11 out of 20 seeds on the 15th day.

Conclusions: according to the results of the above scientific work, it can be concluded that in the 1st method of sterilization germination was 46.667% and seeds germinated from the 9th day, in the second method of sterilization seeds germinated for 15 days, fertility was not observed, fertility index in the third method of sterilization was 55%, seeds germinated from the 6th day. It can be concluded that the third method of sterilization is considered the most convenient for breeding *Dracocephalum moldovica*. species *in vitro*, and a high fertility index can be achieved in a short time.

References:

1. А.В. Сосина, М.Ю. Чередниченко. Индукция каллусогенеза и органогенеза у змееголовника, Молдавского (*Dracocephalum moldavica* L.) *In vitro* известия ТСХА, выпуск 3, 2018
2. Абдуллаева Н.С., Хожиматов О.К., Кубакова К.К. Конспект видов рода *Dracocephalum* L. (Lamiaceae Lindl.)
3. Элинов Н.П. Основы биотехнологии. "Наука", Санкт Петербург 1995 г. – 600 стр.
4. Султонова К. Р., Кушиев Х. Х., Микроклональное размножение *Lagochilus inebrians* Bunge в условиях *in vitro* Бюллетень науки и практики / Bulletin of Science and Practice
5. Т.Г. Волова Биотехнология. Новосибирск: изд. сибирского отделения Российской академии наук, 1999 г. - 252 стр

